

“A Case of Arson & Conspiracy on the Student Leaders of Govt. Arts College, Ananthapur during Freedom Struggle: A Study”

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Introduction :

Govt. Arts College, Ananthapuramu started as the “Ceded Districts College” in 1916, re-named as “Govt. Arts College” in 1947. It is the oldest and most prestigious government institution in the Rayalaseema region and people often call it “The Grand Old Lady of Rayalaseema”. This college has completed 107 years of yeoman service to the noble cause of education and created number of Teachers, Lecturers, Scholars, Civil Servants, Scientists, Philosophers, Judges, Lawyers, Soldiers, Police, Artists, Economists, Journalists, Managers, Social Activists and good Leaders to the society. This college provided good number of efficient Employees for public and private sectors. Arts College shaped the students to occupy from first citizen of India to Local Leaders and Top most All India Civil Servants to Public Servants.

On the occasion of going Azadi Ka Amrit Mahotsav Celebrations, on such a happy and jubilant occasion it behoves on us to look back as this, it is but proper to recall some of the great deeds of those brave children of the college.

Govt. Arts College, Ananthapur- Freedom Struggle :

This Article highlight the sense of commit-

ment evinced by Arts College students during those momentous days of Freedom Struggle and their participation in some political incidents which appear to be, for many of us, the forgotten chapters in the annals of our college. The rationale behind my humble attempt is to create in us awareness that Arts College has produced many good leaders. The national fervour was evoked in them while they were students and the seeds of idealism sown in them later germinated into well-pruned plants with blossoming flowers. We have great respect for these leaders who never swerved from the ideals they cherished. Arts College played an important role in the Freedom movement, though not from the beginning of its establishment in 1916. Arts College students strived hard for the spread of national consciousness among the masses of Rayalaseema. The first phase of the national movement had little impact on the students of our college. When some students began to wear Gandhi caps that were discouraged by the authorities.

A youth league was started with Sri I.Sadasivan, founder-member, as General Secretary and Neelam Sanjiva Reddy, as President. Its motto was to create political consciousness in the youth against the British Rulers and train them in Social Service. Arts College students joined and participated in all its

activities. Later Neelam Sanjiva Reddy became Joint Secretary of the Andhra Provincial Congress Committee. By the efforts of the student members of the youth league, the Freedom movement spread to the other parts of Rayalaseema.

It was at this period a secret cyclostyled local Journal named “Akasavani” was published from the Harijan Hostel under the guidance of Neelam Sanjiva Reddy, I.Sadasivan, Vidwan Viswam and others. It created a stir particularly among the student population. It inculcated anti-war feeling and urged the people to oppose severely the collection of War Fund, compulsory recruitment for war and to expose the evil efforts of imperialism. Arts College students were the only volunteers for the distribution of the journal to the various sections among the masses. Soon the authorities came to know about the anti-British activities and arrested Sri I.Sadasivan, Editor of Akasavni, Sri G.Ramakrishna, local leader, and Sri R. Venkata Naidu, a student of Arts College. Instead of causing demoralization, the arrests infused a fresh vigour and created a stir among the students.

Gandhiji launched individual Satyagraha movement during the first phase of the Second World War in 1940. Then people were not much enlightened politically. They were so much afraid of the British Rule that they hardly had the nerve either to join the Congress or to speak about it. Only a few came out boldly to put up a fight against the British Rule. Many a youth joined the struggle. Neelam Sanjiva Reddy and V.K.Adinarayana Reddy were some of the old students of our college who joined the movement. Sanjiva Reddy was arrested and put be-

hind the bars under the hated Defence of India Rules.

In the month of October 1940, a meeting of the A.P.C.C. was held in the Peace Memorial Hall in Anantapur under the Presidentship of Tanguturi Prakasam. Along with the stalwarts of the Congress such as Neelam Sanjiva Reddy, Kalluru Subba Rao, the Lion of Rayalaseema, Pappuru Ramacharyulu and Cuddapah Koti Reddy two of the college students, namely, Jeevaratnamma and Adisheshaiah, attended the meetings as delegates and spoke for mass Satyagraha instead of individual Satyagraha. That is how the students first identified themselves with the freedom struggle.

Quit India Movement- Arson & Conspiracy Case on the Student Leaders of Govt. Arts College, Ananthapur :

Those were the days when people quaked with fear even to utter the name of Gandhiji. During those momentous days this great College produced such courageous Youngman who, not minding their rosy future, plunged themselves into the freedom struggle and left their indelible remembrances.

The Political activities were at their peak in the years 1940-43. During that period the strength of the college was less than five hundred. Late Sri D.Sanjevaiah was an illustrious student of the college then. A few at those that fought fearlessly the oppressors and the aggressors – the British – are not alive.

C.Adisheshaiah Chetty, a student, became very active in political life. With the result, he was expelled from the College by Sri C.D.S.Chetty, the then Principal. He was later arrested at Tirupathi on the night of 14th Au-

gust, 1942, the year of Quit India Movement. Thus he became the first student to court arrest and to be kept in prison. Gradually the movement gained momentum.

During the Quit India Movement of 1942, our students boycotted classes and went on strike. There was picketing. The police resorted to lathi charges. A lady student, by name Jeevaratnamma, came out boldly and prevailed on the students not to attend classes and led the strike. She was beaten severely by the police faced boldly the lathi charge. Later she went under-ground. The people spoke of her as the Joan of Arc of the College.

After the strike was called off, the students attended the Mid-Term Examination. But on the night of the last day of the Examinations, in the month of September, the Chemistry Laboratory was set on fire and who lit the fire was not known. But the authorities with the collaboration of the then Principal, Sri K.P.G.Menon registered a case of arson & conspiracy against the student leaders- Kotra Gowda, Nanjappa, Channa Basappa, V.K.Adinarayana Reddy, Gangi Reddy, Tirumala Reddy, S.P.Nagi Reddy and against some local leaders.

Channa Basappa later he played a prominent role in Freedom Movement in Bellary District recalled about this Arson & Conspiracy case and said "The period 1939-1944 I spent in this the then only Government College in the whole of Rayalaseema is from all points of view, probably the most significant and turbulent in the history of our Country as well as of this College. Necessarily it is also the most impressive and decisive period of my own life, which formulated and on account of a certain incident

that happened on the night of September 10, 1942, entirely changed the course of my life. As my memory goes back to those turbulent years, a series of epoch-making incidents conjure up before my mind's eye. Declaration of the Second World War... Resignation of Congress Ministers, Individual Satyagraha, and the great escape of Bose... Quit India Movement, Mahadev Desai's death in detention Gandhi's fast unto death... Kasturba's death in Aga Khan Palace... Police firing... Lathi Charge... Students agitation... Setting fire to the Science Laboratory of the College – the biggest sabotage in South India in 1942. Our prosecution in Ordinance Case No.II of 1942 Acquittal. The tumultuous and great applause we received as we walked out of the Court premises....." Even when I had to be thrown out of the Government Hostel in 1943 after my acquittal in the College arson case, my Warden Prof. P.B. Patnaik, called me to his bungalow, gave me light refreshments and told. "I am sorry Channabasappa, I have to obey the Government Order. If you need any help, I shall gladly extend it. Come any time you want." I slowly walked out of his compound and stood alone on the road at the gate leading to the New Block. D.Sanjeevayya and K.B.Narasappa came to my rescue and provided shelter in their room.

Bellary Raghava, the famous artiste of Telugu Theatre, Chandra Sekhara Reddy, Nagarur Narayana Rao and some other advocates pleaded on behalf of the accused in the court. The case was not proved and the students and other leaders were set free.

Conclusion :

Arts College was the only Government College in Rayalaseema then and some of the

Lecturers were also nationalists. All these had influenced the students' movement very much. Arts College students took the lead. People of Rayalaseema were not lagging behind in Freedom Movement. Our student leaders carried the torch of the Freedom struggle to the nook and corner of Rayalaseema and kept it alive till

the country attained freedom on the 15th of August, 1947. This in short is the brilliant saga of the students of this college in Freedom Struggle, It is really thrilling to hear when people narrate the part played by the students who plunged themselves into the freedom struggle without caring for their lives even.

References :

1. RAR Report-2011 of Govt. College, Anantapur.
2. Board of Alumnus List, Govt. College, Anantapur
3. True copy of Ordinance Case II of 42 Court of Special Judge, Anantapur.
4. B.L.Grover & S.Grover; A New Look At Modern Indian History Delhi, S.Chand & Co 1994
5. Bipan Chandra; Modern India, NCERT Delhi
6. Golden Jubilee celebrations Souvenir of Govt. College, Anantapur.

APPENDIX - I

Extract from the Register of Ordinance Case on the file of the Special Judge, Anantapur.
IN THE COURT OF THE SPECIAL JUDGE, ANANTAPUR.

Ordinance Case No. 11 of 42.

Description of the assused

S.No	Name	Father's Name	Caste	Occupation	Residence	Age
1.	A.B.R. Kotra Gowd	Veerappa	Lingayat	Student	Arasanal	22
2.	V.K. Adinarayana Reddy	Rangappa	Kapu	Student	Chimalavagupalli	23
3.	Channabasappa	Veeranna	Lingayat	Student	Alur	21
4.	S.P. Nagi Reddy	Sivarami Reddy	Kapu	Student	Seebavi	19
5.	K. Thirumala Reddy	Banka Reddy	Kapu	Student	Chamalagudur	19
6.	N. Rajasekhara Reddy	Chinnapa Reddy	Kapu	Agriculture	Illur	24
7.	Sadasivan	Chennappa	Lingayat	Harijan Worker	Anantapur	29
8.	Venkatappa	Obeyya	Boya	Employee in a Press	Anantapur	25
9.	Sri G. Venkata Reddy	Venkata Reddy	Kamma	Advocate	Anantapur	32
10.	Sri K.S. Raghava Char	Krishnama Chari	Brahmin	Pleader, Detenu	Anantapur	53
11.	Nanjappa (Pothappa)	Pothappa	Lingayat	Student	Kottur	20
12.	N.C. Gangi Reddi	Chinna Nagireddi	Kapu	Student	Kamalanagar	18
13.	Mallappa	Nagiah	Lingayat	Student	...	21

Date of occurrence :

10-9-1942. Complaint : 26-9-1942. Before the S.S.M., Anantapur. In this Court on 14-11-1942. Apprehension or Appearance – A01 to A-4 on 13-9-1942. A-10 on 15-9-1942. A-11 was a detenuue. A-12 on 22-9-1942. A-13 on 7-10-1942.

Note : A-10 and A-11 were directed to be detained as detenuues under Defence on India

Rules were sentenced in a case under Defence of India Rules.

Release on Bail : Nil. Date of Trail – 14-12-1942.

Close of Trail : 16-12-1942. Order – 17-12-1942.

Signed (not legible),
Sheristedhar, 30-12-1942.
True Copy

